

Personnel- Related Time Management Practices of Head Teachers in Edo State Public Primary Schools

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Abstract

The study investigated personnel-related time management practices of Head teachers in Edo State public primary schools. Four research questions guided the study. The study was a descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised one thousand and forty-two head teachers in Edo State. A multi stage sampling procedure was used for sampling one hundred and four head teachers which represents ten percent selected by random sampling technique in the three Senatorial Districts of Edo State. The Head Teachers' Time Management Practices Questionnaire was used. The Instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisors and three other lecturers from the Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, and University of Benin. The internal consistency reliability of the instrument was determined using the Cronbach's Alpha. The alpha level of 0.70 was obtained. The research questions were answered using frequency counts and simple percentages. The findings of this study revealed that the time management practices of head teachers in public primary schools in Edo State showed majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time performing administrative tasks. The head teachers spent less time on general administrative tasks and instructional supervision administrative tasks. Based on the findings, the study recommended that Head Teachers should spend commensurate amount of time on general administrative tasks to coordinate all school activities with the aim of achieving the objectives of the school effectively and efficiently. Head Teachers should spend more time on instructional supervision administrative tasks as it directly affects teaching and learning.

Key words: Time Management, Head Teachers, Pupil Personnel Administrative Tasks, Staff Personnel Administrative Tasks, School Administration

Introduction

Time management occupies a central position in organizational development because time is one of the most limited and irrecoverable resources available to organizations. Unlike financial or material resources, time cannot be stored, replaced, or expanded; it can only be allocated and utilized more effectively (Bua, 2016; Obiekwe & Mbonu, 2018; Benstowe & Obianwu, 2023., Nnorom, Nwosu & Anyanwu, 2023). As organizations operate in increasingly competitive, complex, and fast-paced environments, the ability to manage time efficiently has become a critical determinant of productivity, adaptability, and long-term growth.

From an organizational development perspective, time management extends beyond individual punctuality or scheduling skills; it reflects how work processes, structures, and cultures are designed to optimize the use of time in achieving organizational goals. Effective time management enables organizations to align tasks with strategic priorities, reduce operational inefficiencies, minimize delays, and improve coordination among units and teams. (Olaifa, Oba- Suleiman, Are, Oshin, & Adeoye, 2023). When time is poorly managed, organizations experience missed deadlines, work overload, role conflict, stress, and reduced quality of output, all of which undermine organizational effectiveness and employee's well-being. A school administrator who coordinates the activities of staff and pupils must be able to manage his time properly in order to accomplish the aims and objectives of the school. (Chukwuemeka, Egboka, & Chukwumobi, 2024). Time management practices refer to the perceived expected time spent in performing administrative tasks. This ensures that the right amount of time is allocated to each activity (Marika, Jagero, kanga & Gitari, 2021; Mgbere and Andrew, 2019; Uwazurike & Anyaogu, 2020). Effective time management practices in a school system will determine the success rate of the school. This is more so in the primary schools which lay the foundation for other levels of education.

Time management further shows how individuals utilise the time allocated to them, in relation to how they accomplish their tasks before the given time elapses. (Olagunju & Asuquo, 2025). Time management includes planning, scheduling, structuring, organising, responsibility, accountability, productivity and other activities relating to making efficient and dynamic use of time. The indicators of effective time management include setting realistic goals, prioritising tasks, involving a team and

effectively handling interruptions. (Lualhati, 2019) Time management requires practice and good planning because it marks the beginning and the end of an operation. An individual can manage time efficiently by setting long term and short term goals, keeping time logs, making to do lists, scheduling and organising an individual's workplace (Adeolu, 2020). Time management can be described as effective planning, setting goals and objectives, setting deadlines, delegation of responsibilities, prioritising activities in relation to their importance and spending the right time on each activity (Anju, 2019).

Head teachers are the heads and managers of primary schools in Nigeria with the responsibility of managing time, making decisions on policies, objectives, and designing the communication network of the school. Therefore, for teachers to perform to the peak of their abilities in a primary school, head teachers must use the right decision-making practices, employ effective time management practices and use the right communication network that would raise teachers' enthusiasm towards hard work while they effectively carry out their administrative tasks. The practices that could help improve school administrators' time management include establishing priorities, managing paperwork, scheduling contacts, handling interruptions, delegating tasks and managing meetings (Akinfolarin, 2017). These time management practices could help identify needs and wants in terms of their importance and match them with time and other resources. They could also bring about orderliness that enables school managers to be more effective and efficient. Without time management, the efficient and effective use of all other school resources might be impossible.

Head teachers are expected to manage, maintain pupil and personnel discipline and welfare (Agih, 2015). The head teachers maintain and improve the buildings and environment as well as the pupils' classrooms, therefore providing a conducive environment for learners to study. The total development of a child can only take place in an environment conducive for teaching and learning. Kielekom, Kanori, and Mugambi (2017) asserted that school administrators spent less time on pupil personnel administrative task. The administrative tasks of school heads under the broad categories of instructional supervision, pupil personnel, staff personnel, school-community relationship, school finance and business management, school plant and general tasks. Alemu (2018) was of the opinion that school administrators spent more time on pupil personnel, community relations, school finance

and business, staff personnel, school plants, instructional supervision and general administrative tasks. Okoka & Akpotu (2025) asserted that school administrators are effectively allocating and utilising time to enhance teaching and learning outcomes. Although Goldring et al (2015) asserted that most school administrators spent less time on instructional supervision administrative tasks. Grissom, Loeb, and Mitani (2015) opined that school administrators spent more time on instructional supervision.

There are needs for administrators to be effective as they carry out these administrative tasks. However, some teachers have complained of inability to meet school targets, propensity to procrastinate, job stress and hasty internal supervision. It seems that head teachers spend a lot of time due to having statutory functions but it appears the head teachers are unable to manage time on other activities as seen in prolonged meetings, frequent interruptions, needless paperwork and memorandum, travelling from one place to another, non-profitable assembly activities, poor delegation, inability to organise and plan their work properly, prolonged personal phone calls, spending much time with drop-in visitors and involving in routines and duties that should have been delegated amongst others. It appears that the head teachers are busy with one task or another, and as such do not attend to other serious issues like handling disciplinary cases of pupils, extracurricular activities, maintaining positive relationship among staff including stimulating and providing opportunities for professional growth. This is more so, that they operate within a limited time frame and this could affect other administrative tasks that needs to be carried out on a daily basis. Could this perceived mismanagement of time, by head teachers be responsible for their inability to carry out their statutory administrative tasks effectively?

It is on this premise that this study investigated the personnel-related time management practices of head teachers in Edo State public primary schools.

Research Questions

To provide a direction for this study, the following research questions were raised:

1. What are the time management practices on general administrative tasks?
2. What are the time management practices on instructional supervision?

3. What are the time management practices on pupil personnel?
4. What are the time management practices on staff personnel?

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design which enabled the researcher to collect factual information from a sample of the specified population to describe the characteristics of the population as they exist in their natural setting without manipulating variables. The population of this study comprised of all one thousand and forty-two (1042) head teachers, one thousand and forty-two (1042) public primary schools. One hundred and four (104) head teachers and one hundred and four (104) schools were sampled for the study, which was approximately ten percent (10%) of the population of head teachers and public primary schools in Edo State. The sampling procedure used for the study was the multi-stage sampling procedure. This was done to have adequate representation. The state was stratified into three senatorial districts using the stratified technique. Then ten percent (10%) of head teachers and schools were randomly selected using the simple random sampling techniques.

The research instruments used for the study was titled “Head teachers' Time Management Practices Questionnaire” (HTMPQ). It was used to seek information on the time management practices of head teachers in public primary schools in Edo State. The questionnaire was separated into two sections, section A and B. Section A contained questions that gave demographic details of the school and head teachers. Section B contained questions that sought information on the different personnel-related time management practices used by the head teachers. A modified Likert scale was used in the questionnaire. The response option was designed in a modified Likert scale format.

A content validity of the questionnaire was established by the researcher’s supervisors and three other lecturers in the Department of Educational Management, University of Benin, Benin City. The research instrument were critically examined to ensure that the contents of the research instrument was relevant to the topic, unambiguous and rated the extent to which items appears to measure the perception sought. The corrections and contributions made were incorporated into the final questionnaire. The questionnaire was first administered to 20 head teachers in public primary schools in Edo state. This group of head teachers were excluded from the main body of head teachers that

later made up the respondents of the questionnaire used for this study. The internal consistency was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha method. The alpha level of 0.70 was obtained on the instrument. The reliability value showed that the instrument was reliable for this study.

The questionnaires were administered to the respondents by the researcher and one research assistant per school. The research assistants helped to monitor the questionnaire and informed the researcher when to retrieve the filled questionnaire. One hundred percent (100%) of the questionnaires administered to Head Teachers was retrieved .

Results

Data collected were collated and analyzed using frequency counts and percentages. Decision rule was based on percentages used to show time management practices for the research questions.

Research question 1: What are the time management practices on general administrative tasks?

Table 1: Time Management Practices on General Administrative Tasks

S/N	Statements	1-15 mins		16-30 mins		31mins-1 hr		Above 1hr		Perceived expected time
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
1	Coordinating of assemblies.	30	28.8	0	0	17	16.3	57	54.8	1-15mins
2	Attending and presiding over staff meeting.	18	17.3	45	43.3	25	24.0	16	15.4	Above 1hr
3	Attending school functions such as interhouse sports, orientation and graduation programme.	87	83.7	4	3.8	9	8.7	4	3.8	Above 1hr
4	Organising administrative seminars and workshop.	67	64.4	29	27.9	4	3.8	4	3.8	Above 1hr
5	Keeping school records.	43	41.3	16	15.4	12	11.5	33	31.7	16-30mins

Table 1 shows that on general administrative tasks, majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time. The head teachers spent less time on general administrative tasks. This

implies that head teachers’ time management practices are not in line with the perceived expected time.

Research question 2: What are the time management practices on instructional supervision?

Table 2: Time Management Practices on Instructional Supervision

S/N	Statements	1-15 mins		16-30 mins		31mins-1 hr		Above 1hr		Perceived expected time
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
6	Conducting short teacher observation.	17	16.3	17	16.3	25	24.0	45	43.3	1-15mins
7	Conducting long teacher observation.	34	32.7	33	31.7	33	31.7	4	3.8	16-30mins
8	Monitoring to ensure that teaching and learning is carried out at the proper time allocated.	26	25.0	16	15.4	17	16.3	45	43.3	16-30mins
9	Monitoring to ensure that assignments are given and marked as at when due.	18	17.3	8	7.7	45	43.3	33	31.7	16-30mins
10	Ensuring that hotspot is available for teachers to update their smartphones to enable the work of the day get to the centre unit after synchronizing.	26	25.0	17	16.3	12	11.5	49	47.1	31mins-1hr
11	Monitoring to make sure that teachers preview their lesson.	9	8.7	20	19.2	34	32.7	41	39.4	Above 1 hr

Table 2 shows that on instructional supervision, majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time. The head teachers spent less time on instructional supervision administrative tasks.

Research question 3: What are the time management practices on pupil personnel?

Table 3: Time Management Practices on Pupil Personnel

S/N	Statements	1-15 mins		16-30 mins		31mins-1 hr		Above 1hr		Perceived expected time
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
12	Providing guidance and counselling service to pupils.	38	36.5	25	24.0	21	20.2	20	19.2	16-30mins
13	Supervising to ensure the pupils attendance register is marked daily by teachers.	5	4.8	4	3.8	24	23.1	71	68.3	1-15mins
14	Handling disciplinary cases promptly.	29	27.9	20	19.2	38	36.5	17	16.3	16-30mins
15	Monitoring to ensure pupils safety in school.	38	36.5	17	16.3	37	35.6	12	11.5	16-30mins
16	Checking proper dressing of pupils.	17	16.3	8	7.7	21	20.2	58	55.8	16-30mins
17	Admission of new pupils.	21	20.2	12	11.5	38	36.5	33	31.7	1-15mins

Table 3 shows that on pupil personnel, head teachers' time management practices shows that majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time. The head teachers spent more time on pupil personnel administrative tasks.

Research question 4: What are the time management practices on staff personnel?

Table 4: Time Management Practices on Staff Personnel

S/N	Statements	1-15 mins		16-30 mins		31mins-1 hr		Above 1hr		Perceived expected time
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
18	Putting on hotspot to enable teachers mark their arrival at the school.	17	16.3	8	7.7	21	20.2	58	55.8	Above 1hr
19	Opening of the smartphone for teachers to mark departure.	17	16.3	0	0	4	3.8	83	79.8	Above 1hr
20	Supervising to ensure teachers are teaching with the right teaching materials using their smartphone.	26	25.0	20	19.2	33	31.7	25	24.0	16-30mins

21	Attending to individual needs of teachers as regards teaching.	21	20.2	16	15.4	25	24.0	42	40.4	16-30mins
22	Regularly checks performance to ensure improvement of teachers.	22	21.2	24	23.1	25	24.0	33	31.7	16-30mins

Table 4 shows that on staff personnel, majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time. Head Teachers spent less time on staff personnel administrative tasks.

Discussion of findings

The findings from research question one revealed that majority of the head teachers do not spend the perceived expected time in performing general tasks administrative tasks. The head teachers spent less time on general administrative tasks. This may be as a result of poor delegation, frequent interruptions by visitors, unnecessary telephone calls and unscheduled meetings. This finding disagrees with the findings of Alemu (2018) that administrators spends more time on general tasks.

The findings from research question two reveals that majority of the head teachers do not spend the perceived expected time in performing instructional supervisory administrative tasks. The head teachers spent less time on instructional supervision administrative tasks. This may be as a result of frequent interruptions, receiving personal phone calls, ineffectively handling interruptions and managing time and attending to other administrative tasks that could have been handled conveniently later. This finding agrees with Goldring et al (2015) which stated that administrators do not spend enough time in classrooms or focus on teaching and learning but also called for more research to understand how implementation of teachers observations and their use affect administrator's effectiveness, views and roles. This finding disagrees with the findings of Grissom, et al (2015) on time use and effectiveness carried out in Miami-Dade County public schools which revealed that school administrators allocated more time to managing instruction in their schools. They also found out that administrators who are capable of managing their time better spend more time on instruction management in schools when compared to the other tasks.

Moreso the findings from research question three revealed that majority of the head teachers do not spend the perceived expected time in performing pupil personnel administrative tasks. The head teachers spent more time on pupil personnel administrative tasks. This may be as a result of the head teachers ineffectively handling interruptions and managing time. This finding disagrees with Kielekom et al (2017) that stated that administrator spends less time on pupil personnel administrative tasks as a result of work load and agrees with Alemu (2018) that stated that administrators spends more time on pupil personnel administrative tasks. The findings from research question four revealed that majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time on staff personnel administrative tasks. Head Teachers spent less time on staff personnel administrative tasks. This could be as a result of the head teachers ineffectively handling interruptions and managing time. This finding disagrees with the findings of Alemu (2018) that administrators spends more time on staff personnel administrative tasks.

Conclusion

Time is one of the resources an administrator needs for efficient management in order to achieve organizational goals. The study established that the time management practices of head teachers of public primary schools shows that majority of the head teachers did not spend the perceived expected time in performing administrative tasks. The head teachers spent less time on general administrative tasks and instructional supervision administrative tasks. Although the head teachers spent more time on pupil personnel administrative tasks, the head teachers spent less time on staff personnel administrative tasks. The fact that head teachers were not spending the perceived expected time on administrative tasks may be as a result of poor delegation, inefficiently handling interruptions. Therefore if head teachers can improve on their personnel-related time management practices they will be more efficient in achieving the goals and objectives of the school.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

1. Head Teachers should spend commensurate amount of time on general administrative tasks to coordinate all school activities with the aim of achieving the objectives of the school effectively and efficiently.

2. Head Teachers should spend more time on instructional supervision administrative tasks as it directly affects teaching and learning.

3. Head Teachers should be given adequate training in the form of workshops, seminars and meetings by the Ministry of Education to make them more efficient in their pupil personnel administrative tasks time management practices.

4. Head Teachers should spend commensurate amount of time on staff personnel administrative tasks since it determines the strength and weaknesses of a teacher, as well as providing adequate teaching resources and professional development for teachers to achieve the organisation goals and objectives.

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